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DELIVERABLE 4.7 – INTERACTION SEQUENCE MODELS (FINAL VERSION)

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Executive summary

This deliverable summarizes a task-based analysis of our 9 use case (UC) scenarios. We integrated a theory-driven modelling approach called interaction sequence modelling. With this approach we were able to identify key information requirements in the scope of real machine operation procedures and behaviour. The presented interaction sequence models, based on Norman's Human Action Cycle, focus on information retrieval and the integration of XR technology to enhance vehicle operators' awareness and performance. The models emphasize improving information design and retrieval processes, moving away from traditional small screens. We also included the findings of user research within the transdisciplinary co-design approach (WP3) to discuss our preliminary HMI-concept, postulated in WP3 and 4 so far.

For UC1, snow grooming, three key scenarios are discussed, addressing challenges such as diverting the operator's attention during adjustments, constant checks for obstacles affecting attention, and the safety risks associated with reduced visibility in adverse weather conditions. We identified a set of important information operators rely on when executing associated tasks and that operators mainly focus the environment and blade during these activities.

For UC2, logistics, three key scenarios were modelled: Picking up containers, placing containers, and collision avoidance during transport. Challenges include visually estimating precise spreader positioning and frequent manual checks for obstacles. We identified a set of important information operators rely on when executing associated tasks and that operators again mainly focus the environment and spreader during these activities.

For UC3, construction, three key scenarios are discussed. These scenarios include achieving precise depth control during grading, obstacle and person detection, and the infield design process for excavation pits. Challenges included constant depth checking during grading, limited visibility behind the boom, and a time-consuming calibration process in infield design. We identified a set of important information operators rely on when executing associated tasks and that operators again mainly focus the environment and bucket during these activities.

In modelling information requirements and attentional focus pattern we identified further requirements for presenting information and interaction through XR technologies that enable a better integration in user workflows. The conceptual XR-technologies that we discussed in the context of this scenario analysis involved real-time projection of information in the environment, highlight obstacles with lights, display-based augmented camera streams and 3D visualizations as well as haptic and peripheral light feedback to present information about obstacles, missions, tool accuracy and current and planned environment conditions at the right place at the right time.

The interaction sequence models provide a formalized framework for describing XR interaction within machine operation tasks, considering human perception and processing capabilities. These models serve as a tool for multi-disciplinary discussions. This foundational work lays the groundwork for subsequent technical development and integration within the project but also could serve as a handy tool in any R&D-project in the realm of multimodal user interfaces. A blanked version of our analysis framework can be found in the appendix.

Table of Contents

Document Identification.....	2
Executive summary.....	4
1 Introduction	6
2 Interaction sequence modelling	7
3 Use case-specific interaction sequence models	9
3.1 UC1: Snow grooming.....	9
3.2 UC2: Logistics	13
3.3 UC3: Construction	17
4 Conclusion.....	21
References.....	22
Appendix 1 – Analysis Framework.....	24

List of Figures

Figure 1: Seven stages of action [2].....	7
Figure 2: Example interaction sequence	8
Figure 3: Snow-groomer cabin view. Snow depth measurement system screen in the bottom middle.....	9
Figure 4: Interaction sequence model for UC1 scenario 1.....	10
Figure 5: Interaction sequence model for UC1 scenario 2.....	11
Figure 6: Interaction sequence model for UC1 scenario 3.....	12
Figure 7: Reach stacker cabin view. Green lights indicate locked twist locks.....	13
Figure 8: Interaction sequence model for UC2 scenario 1.....	14
Figure 9: Interaction sequence model for UC2 scenario 2.....	15
Figure 10: Interaction sequence model for UC2 scenario 3	16
Figure 11: Excavator cabin view.	17
Figure 12: Interaction sequence model for UC3 scenario 1.....	18
Figure 13: Interaction sequence model for UC3 scenario 2.....	19
Figure 14: Interaction sequence model for UC3 scenario 3.....	20

1 Introduction

Presenting information and interacting with machine functions, assistive systems and digital data via extended reality (XR) technologies promise easier access to these systems. However, to fully unlock their potential, XR technologies must be carefully designed and implemented into the operators' operation procedures. Only if they manage to provide real performance, usability and user experience benefits over conventional display-based they will be accepted and valued. Attention allocation, information needs in these operation procedures as well as the cognitive processing behind these operation procedures play an important role in adequately designing XR interaction.

Task 4.3 analyses these identified information components and interaction flows (e.g., described in WP3 and 4) in a systematic and model-based way to derive specifications for XR interactions in our cyber-physical system use cases. This analysis required the previous identification of key tasks in all use case-based work scenarios. Also, the transdisciplinary scenario-based co-design approach (T3.2) and its user research activities such as the contextual inquiries described in D3.1 provided further contextual foci. In understanding the operators' workflows and associated thoughts and ideas, these provided a set of key assets that were then analyzed in detail in T4.3. As an extensional approach to co-design, this task applied theoretical and model-based analysis procedures stemming from the knowledge engineering domain, covering methods such as the cognitive work analysis approach. For this task we adopted different task analysis approaches such as hierarchical task analysis in integrating our interaction sequence model approach to describe how operators deal with different tasks as a sequence of different information retrieving and processing steps in the context of cognitive constraints and reasoning.

In the following chapters, the theoretical background and our adaptation of the interaction sequence models will be described. We will then present interaction sequence models for all three use-cases, outlining the initial (problematic) situation and possible (conceptual) solutions for three use-case scenarios each. Finally, the further use of these models in the HMI design and development process will be discussed.

2 Interaction sequence modelling

The development and integration of XR Technology into operation environments for machine operators aims at improving information transfer, perception and processing on the operators' side compared to display-based information presentation and interaction that are the standard way of integrating digital information systems into off-highway machines today. In overlaying digital information on physical perception, XR technologies have the potential to improve the operators' perception, situation awareness, and cognitive workload [e.g. 1,2] eventually resulting in increased work performance [2], ease of use and thus technology acceptance [3]. However, to leverage this potential XR information presentation must be implemented very carefully to present the right information at the right time in the right form. To identify the involved constraints, we integrated and applied interaction sequence models.

State of the art task analysis methods from the knowledge engineering domain such as hierarchical task analysis [4] decomposes complex operation procedures into more specific sub-tasks. At the lowest level, this decomposition could differentiate single mental activities such as information, perception, evaluation, intention planning and action execution that form the fundamental steps in humans' behaviour. However, in conventional HTA approaches this result in vast amounts of components that do not represent real life task sequences. Additionally, in understanding real live operation procedures, these must be understood as an entangled sequence of information perception and action steps that build on each other. Another important aspect is the fact that especially industrial work procedures are highly goal driven. In other words, operators often aim to fulfil specific goals (e.g., ensure safety, reach a defined work result) in applying their knowledge, experience and perception of the outside world in controlling a machine adequately. Therefore, Norman's Human Action Cycle (aka "seven stages of action", see Figure 1 [5][6], a commonly used model in the field of knowledge engineering, was adopted as a central approach to interaction modelling. His original cycle of interaction stages consists of forming an intention, selecting an action, executing the action and evaluating the outcome in relation to the goal [5].

Figure 1: Seven stages of action [2]

The important take away is, that we must understand machine operation as a continuous sequence of such "cognitive perception and action" loops where the behavioural result of one loop (e.g. activating a certain machine function) alters the outside world triggering the next loop to evaluate the consequences and again informing a suitable behavioural reaction. Together with other analytic procedures in work domain analysis, knowledge engineering provides a powerful approach to understand how humans act in technical systems. However, these approaches easily produce very complex and hard to work with descriptive models that often fail to provide focuses design recommendations.

Therefore, we integrated the interaction sequence model approach that applied the same descriptive methods such as HTA [4] and WDA [7] but also applies several selection criteria to focus on important steps and loops that represent important information presentation constraints. Another addition is the consideration of several loops and tasks as a continuous sequence capable to model more complex tasks and activities that build upon each other. The result is a detailed decomposition of operation tasks into a sequence of different stages of information retrieving and action making, in the context of goals, reasoning and system-based constraints that help us to understand where XR technologies can help to improve information presentation and interaction [8].

Figure 2: Example interaction sequence

As in the example model (see Figure 2), our modelling procedure starts in identifying the involved work goals (in this example: ensuring safety). This goal results in action intentions and actions that the operator performs to reach it. Each action results in an insight (as a result of information retrieval and evaluation) which then again results in a follow up action intention. In focusing on exemplary subtasks and sequential activities of information extraction and reasoning our models are capable to cover complex operation procedures and influencing effects of human attentional resources and system constraints. To identify the steps involved, we used the insights of expert discussions and our user research studies. The example case ends after the operator has checked all information sources to conclude that no safety risk is imminent. Of course, this is an ongoing activity in itself as each machine movement and the dynamic reality outside continuously changes. However, we do not loop back to the intent as in the original human action cycle since we consider the intent of task completion to be ongoing. Also, this goal-driven task of ensuring safety does not occur in isolation. Instead, it is rather a side task associated to another task that is the machine and tool manoeuvring to reach another work goal. Thus, several goals and associated actions are entangled in real life machine operation. However, even when operators are capable of recognizing these different aspects in all their actions at the same time, especially attention allocation, information perception and action execution is often limited to one aspect at the time, resulting in a continuous shift of foci [9]. However, these models provide valuable insights regarding information requirements, the attentional modes and the cognitive procedures that operators apply and provide constraints and requirements that can be considered in interaction design.

In the following chapters we present the condensed interaction sequence models for all use cases scenarios. These models overlay both the existing (initial) and the future (conceptual) operating situations to show the (partially problematic) status quo and planned XR and information design improvements. The conceptual models are based on the activity scenarios created in T3.2. Thus, the conceptual models not only represent ideas of possible XR solutions we explore but also provide guiding constraints regarding their design.

3 Use case-specific interaction sequence models

3.1 UC1: Snow grooming

In use case 1, snow grooming, we modelled the initial situations, and visionary interaction flows of the following three scenarios:

1. Build slope matching target surface
2. Collision avoidance
3. Zero-sight navigation

Scenario 1 presents the main job of snow groomer operators on the slope. Building the slope to match the required target surface involves preparing a smooth surface, maintaining slope borders, adding and removing snow, moving excess snow to other parts of the slope and avoiding damages to the surface (e.g., accidentally ripping the ground open with the blade, causing snow and soil to mix, or using a wrong configuration of the blade wings, causing chunks of snow to escape and possibly damage the already finished parts of the slope). Thus, realizing the target surface is considered the main goal, that can be decomposed in a set of sub-goals that are: applying a suitable depth and angle to the blade; applying a suitable machine speed; manoeuvring the machine to cover the work area. In the model below (see Figure 4), we focus on the main task of matching the target surface, which requires knowledge of current and target snow depth (**information requirements**). Today, this is usually handled with an on-board system that shows the delta between current and target snow depth, visualized with a heatmap where specific colours indicate a lack or excess of snow (see Figure 3). Checking the delta and adjusting the blade accordingly requires repeated checking of the map data on a screen, which may be on the side or near the bottom of the cabin, thus, taking away the operator's attention from the operating area in front. Adjustment of the tiller is depending on snow conditions and needs to be done based on the operator's knowledge and experience.

Figure 3: Snow-groomer cabin view. Snow depth measurement system screen in the bottom middle.

Figure 4: Interaction sequence model for UC1 scenario 1.

We identified that snow groomer operators depend on information about the snow depth in front of the vehicle in different distances to plan and execute a proper vehicle manoeuvring strategy and blade handling. Also, information regarding the work result (behind the machine) is important. Operators continuously shift their attention between this information to adapt machine controls to achieve the main goal of creating the target surface profile.

As operators of conventional machines must shift their attention between the display-based interface and the environment all the time with significant interpretation efforts to overlay the display-based information XR technologies can be used to implement this information closer to the peripheral sight when looking outside the cabin and into the physical controls.

Figure 4 also highlight a set of XR solutions we consider effective in easing access to this information while focusing on the outside and machine operation controls. In our vision, information on target snow depth, and current depth deviation across the whole work area (in front and behind the machine) as well as positioning indicators for blade (and potentially tiller) adjustments can be presented through a set of XR techniques: (1) snow depth, depth deviation, work area boarders, planned movement path and positioning indicators for the tools can presented via a projection onto the snow surface, (2) depth deviation behind the machine can be presented trough an light feedback system on the front window, and (3) speed and manoeuvring indicators can be presented as haptic feedback in the track controls. This has the potential to facilitate operation as the operators can keep their eyes on the terrain in front of the vehicle.

Scenario 2 presents handling with the very common threat of being involved in accidents, whether with obstacles (e.g., snow cannons or other equipment left behind on the slope) or skiers that regularly still use the slope even after closing hours. Avoiding collisions is the main goal in this scenario. As visualized in this model (see Figure 5), to detect obstacles or skiers and react accordingly, operators need to check the front area in a long distance, mirrors, sides and, if available, the rear-view camera of their vehicle near constantly. This obviously demands high alertness from the operator and takes away a lot of attention from the main operating area in the front of the vehicle.

Figure 5: Interaction sequence model for UC1 scenario 2.

We identified “presence of an obstacle”, “type of obstacle”, “movement path”, “machine heading”, “machine size” and “speed” as key information operators require to avoid collisions. Operators must divert focus from monitoring tool and machine handling to observing the environment which involves the regular use of display-based presentations of camera streams and mirrors.

Figure 5 also highlight a set of XR solutions we consider effective in easing access to this information while focusing on the outside and machine operation controls. When obstacles, e.g., skiers or animals in vicinity of the vehicle are detected, their presence could be visualized via light feedback system in the front of the cabin and/or light bars around the frame of existing on-board system screens. The type of obstacle (immobile object, animal, human, etc.) and its proximity could be conveyed via hue and size of the lit-up area (red and large area may indicate a human in proximity, yellow and small area may indicate an immobile object further away). This information presentation could be associated with sound signals and vibration feedback in track controls to increase information salience.

Scenario 3 presents a dangerous situation in which the operator is faced with fog, heavy snowfall or a snowstorm, capable of significantly reducing vision or taking it away entirely (whiteout). Avoiding collisions and maintaining the correct movement path of the machine are considered key goals in this scenario (see Figure 6). The operator may then try to navigate using known landmarks (e.g., trees, slope borders, immobile snow cannons) in combination with on-board map systems (if available). Trying to identify objects and the whole environment under such conditions dramatically increases workload and visual attention. Navigating the slope without knowledge of location and/or orientation may result in major accidents, putting both vehicle and operator at risk.

Figure 6: Interaction sequence model for UC1 scenario 3.

We identified the important role of digital information regarding the outside environment and obstacles as key information requirements in this scenario where operators' direct visual perception of the environment is strongly limited. As such situations can be very stressful and demanding, digital information such as vehicle position, work area and planned movement paths, as well as obstacles in the environment should be represented in a simple and easy to grasp way. However, as sensors might be also compromised in such conditions, monitoring the outside through the windows is still essential and careful manoeuvring with suitable speeds is advised. Digital data and user interfaces should remind operators to double check even in poor visibility conditions.

A possible solution for this scenario could be the projection of real-time map data, navigation and orientation information directly onto the windshield (or other surfaces in the cabin), onto the snow in front of the vehicle or even a projection into the fog ahead. The operator could rely completely on the guidance provided by the on-board XR system to navigate to safety or continue their snow-grooming routine, even in a complete whiteout scenario.

3.2 UC2: Logistics

In use case 2, logistics, we modelled the initial situations and conceptual interaction sequences of the following scenarios:

1. Picking up container (from ground or stack)
2. Placing container (on ground or stack)
3. Collision avoidance

All three scenarios are embedded in the reach stacker operators' main workflow with only minor differences in execution depending on whether a container needs to be picked up from- or placed onto the ground, a stack or truck trailer respectively.

The first scenario involves accurately positioning the spreader on top of a container as the main goal of interaction. This requires the operator to approach the container with the vehicle, positioning the spreader accurately above it, locking the twist locks, raising the container and bringing it into a safe driving position for moving it to its target location. To position the spreader, operators ideally manoeuvre the machine in a centred frontal approach. When positioning the spreader above the container, assessing the necessary movements and adjustments of vehicle, boom and spreader to align the spreader with the container precisely can prove difficult due to the reliance on visual estimation (see Figure 8) regarding distance to container, alignment with centre line and height of the spreader. Once the spreader is in the right position, locking the twist locks happens automatically or with the press of a button. The status of the twist locks is visualized with coloured lights on an upper beam in the cabin and on the spreader itself (see Figure 7). While learning the basic mechanics of operating the vehicle and picking up containers is easy, doing this job efficiently requires a lot of experience.

Figure 7: Reach stacker cabin view. Green lights indicate locked twist locks.

Figure 8: Interaction sequence model for UC2 scenario 1.

We identified “distance to container”, “position of the spreader’s connectors relative to the container's connectors” and “status of locking” as key information in this scenario. While already assisted with light feedback for the locking status the other information needs to be exclusively retrieved from direct vision and visual estimation. Overlaying the camera stream showing the spreader and the container with a visual representation of the position deviation could assist the operator in manoeuvring the machine and positioning the spreader. A possible solution for this would be a projection of transparent beams extending downwards from the twist locks as well as numerical indicators that qualify the distances in display-based XR. Also calibrated artificial camera perspectives that allow for a bird’s eye view onto the spreader and container could help the operator to extend its perception of the situation. Such visualizations could make the visual estimation of the correct positioning of the spreader above the container much easier and more efficient. The colour of these XR beams could indicate the correct positioning of the twist locks above the container corners, or their incorrect positioning respectively (see Figure 7).

The second scenario is essentially a similar process as the picking up but focusing on the lower corners of the container instead (see Figure 9). Thus, the goals are very similar as operators’ want to accurately position the vehicle and the spreader on top of a container at a designated position on the ground. Therefore, operators estimate the position of the cargo from direct sight. Especially in high drop off positions this is much more difficult. When the container is positioned correctly, the twist locks need to be manually unlocked by pressing a button. Unlike the container pick-up process, where the twist locks would audibly “snap” into the openings in the corners of the container, there is no such additional feedback of a correct release when placing a container.

Figure 9: Interaction sequence model for UC2 scenario 2.

Again, distance of the spreader (and picked up container) to target drop of position in all three spatial dimensions is the key information requirement in this scenario.

Besides operators focus on the ground surface of the container, the same solution as in scenario 1 would apply, with the simple adjustment of the XR beams extending downward through the picked-up container and into the ground (see Figure 8). This would facilitate the placement process just like the positioning of the spreader when picking up a container.

Finally, **scenario 3**, the checking for objects, persons and vehicles in the vicinity of the reach stacker happens repeatedly, usually after the completed picking-up and placement processes, whenever the reach stacker is being driven to another location. Avoiding collisions is the key goal of this scenario. This involves movement clearance for the vehicle as well as for the spreader and loaded container. Checking the vicinity requires looking into the side mirrors (front or middle position, depending on the cabin position) and the rear window (see Figure 10). In some machines, rear cameras may be available, but we did not see an example for this on the user research visits. However, we expect this to be a similar technical setup as in snow-groomers or excavators (see Figure 4 and Figure 12).

Similar to use-case 1, we identified “presence of an obstacle”, “type of obstacle”, “movement path of obstacle”, “movement of machine and cargo”, “position offset between actual position and target position” and “speed” as key information operators require to avoid collisions. Operators must divert focus from monitoring tool and machine handling to observing the environment which involves the regular use of display-based presentations of camera streams and mirrors.

Figure 10: Interaction sequence model for UC2 scenario 3

To solve this problem, objects such as other vehicles or persons moving around the container terminal could be detected via thermal cameras both from the vehicle or from large stationary floodlight posts overlooking the area. Detected objects could be identified and highlighted in the XR view, e.g., by making their contours visible behind rows of container stacks or indicating their relative position to the vehicle with directional markers in the operator’s field of view. This way, operators would need to check the mirrors much less often, perceiving other vehicles or persons in the area passively. Also, a solution similar to light feedback in display-based XR could help to present this information in a non-complex way.

3.3 UC3: Construction

In use case 3, construction, we modelled the initial situations and conceptual interaction sequences of the following three scenarios:

1. Finish grading
2. Obstacle and person detection and avoidance
3. Infield design

The first scenario again represents the main job for the excavator operator: Creating an even surface at the target depth for an excavation pit or trench. The key goal in this scenario is to ensure a steady and accurate height of the tool throughout moving it towards the machine. This involves excavating a previously defined pit or trench layer by layer without damaging any structures (e.g., power, gas or water lines) possibly hidden below that target depth. Creating an even surface at the exact target depth is a challenge that only very experienced operators will master without technological assistance systems or manual labour as several hydraulics must be operated at the same time to realize a plane tool movement trajectory. For less experienced operators or trainees, assistance systems are sometimes available, but these require near constant checking of the bucket's current depth in relation to the target depth, usually indicated on an on-board screen (see Figure 11). Paying attention to both screen information and real movement of the boom and bucket thus requires shifting the focus repeatedly, significantly slowing down the operation.

Figure 11: Excavator cabin view.

We identified tool trajectory, height deviation and angle of boom, stick and tool as well as ground clearance as the key information in this scenario. Experienced operators are capable of retrieving this information purely from direct sight. But also, state-of-the-art assistive systems display e.g. height deviation on the terminal display.

A possible solution for this would be to use an LED panel on the boom or a laser projection on the ground to visualize the bucket's depth in relation to the target depth close to the area where the operator would usually focus (see Figure 11). This would remove the need to shift focus and make vehicle operation using such an assistance system much more efficient.

Figure 12: Interaction sequence model for UC3 scenario 1.

Scenario 2 resembles the obstacle and person detection, and avoidance discussed in UC1 scenario 2 with the same goal: avoiding collisions. In this use case, other workers, vehicles and possibly pedestrians passing (or trespassing) within the construction site need to be recognized and avoided. Visibility is especially limited on the right side of the vehicle behind the boom. Operators need to continuously check the outside through windows, mirrors and camera streams presented on a separate surveillance display in the cabin while moving the tool or machine.

As in the other use cases, we identified “presence of an obstacle”, “type of obstacle” and “movement path of vehicle” “movement of boom and bucket”, and “upper carriage heading, size and speed” as key information, operators require to avoid collisions. Operators must divert focus from monitoring the tool and handling the machine to observing the environment, which involves the regular use of display-based presentations of camera streams and mirrors.

This scenario can be approached in the same way as UC1 scenario 2 using ambient lights around the cabin front and/or on-board system screens (see Figure 13).

Figure 13: Interaction sequence model for UC3 scenario 2.

Finally, **scenario 3** involves the creation of a digital excavation pit/trench model using the on-board systems, a task also called infield design. This requires the corners of the planned excavation pit to be set up using real world markings (e.g., using rods, bricks, etc.) which must then be approached with the excavator bucket to calibrate the system and register the pit dimensions in the digital model. This is usually a complicated and time-consuming process that may require a complete restart if errors or inaccuracies are detected. We also found that operators have difficulties aligning the abstract virtual representation of machine and environment with their real work area.

We identified “location of corners of the virtual geometry grid” as the key information and the creation of such corners and their movement as the key interaction requirement in this scenario.

This can be solved by using LiDAR to register the corners of the planned excavation pit, projecting the outlines of the defined pit directly onto the ground or augmenting a camera view of the excavation pit with these outlines (see Figure 14). Also using the tool to manipulate the geometry or a laser projection on the ground can help to better connect the real construction pit with its digital twin.

Figure 14: Interaction sequence model for UC3 scenario 3.

4 Conclusion

The interaction sequence models reconstruct information retrieval and processing activities as well as attentional focus patterns. In addition to our co-design user research, this systemic analysis provides further evidence about when which information is needed, where it should be presented and in what contexts it needs to be understood by the operator. This enables a much more fine-tuned design of XR interaction. We further improved the interaction sequence model framework that in its current form can visualize how in many of these use case scenarios the act of looking at a screen interrupts the operators' focus on the main operating area, especially where precise adaptation to a continuously changing situation is needed. The conceptual interaction sequence models also highlight beneficial information presentation solutions that are being explored in XR techniques in the project. They also show how in some cases, the same technical developments can be used in different use-cases: Ambient lights may highlight obstacles and persons in the vicinity of vehicles, laser projections on the ground may be used to light the way or indicate tool adjustments. Thus, we expect XR, and information design developments made in this project to be generally applicable to other off-highway domains as well, such as agriculture or mining.

The XR interaction concepts described by these sequence models provide a basis for technological discussion, exploration and development of solutions, as the last chapter shows. Prototyping and/or development of some of these solutions has already started. In the next months, along with the progress of WP3 and WP4 in general, the interaction sequence models will be updated and elaborated.

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ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

HMI	Human machine interface
HTA	Hierarchical task analysis
R&D	Research & development
UC	Use Case
WDA	Work domain analysis
XR	Extended Reality

Appendix 1 – Analysis Framework

